

The Effect Of Implementation Of Government Institution Performance Accountability System On The Implementation Of Good Governance In Musi Banyuasin District, South Sumatera Province, Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 15, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Government Institution Performance Accountability System, Good Governance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5576743</p>	<p><i>Accountability is the responsibility of the obligation to account for the success or failure in carrying out the organization's mission in achieving the goals and targets that have been set through a media of accountability periodically. As a follow up in eradicating the practice of Collusion of Corruption and Nepotism as mandated by Law Number 28 of 1999, in the context of further improving the implementation of a more efficient, effective, clean and responsible government. Government Policy through Presidential Instruction No. 7 of 1999 issued regulations regarding the Accountability of Government Agencies' Performance so that good governance was created. The purpose of this study is to find out: (1) Implementation of Performance Accountability System of Government Agencies in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency (2) Implementation of good governance in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency (3) How much influence the implementation of Government Institution Performance Accountability System the application of good governance in the Regional Personnel Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency. The method used in this research is analytical descriptive with survey approach. Whereas to analyze the data obtained used the moment Product Correlation Coefficient Analysis, Determinant Coefficient Test and Hypothesis Test using the Significance Test (t Test). The results obtained are: (1) Implementation of the Accountability System of Government Agencies' Performance in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency, including very good classification. (2) the application of Good Governance in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency is included in the very good classification. (3) The implementation of the Government Agency Performance Accountability System has a significant effect on the implementation of Good Governance in the Regional Personnel Agency office in Musi Banyuasin.</i></p>

Introduction

The implementation of good governance is a prerequisite for governance in realizing the aspirations of the people and achieving the ideals of the nation and state. For this reason, it is necessary to develop and implement a measurable and legitimate system of accountability so that government administrators and development take place in an effective, effective, clean and responsible manner and free from a culture of corruption, collusion and nepotism.

The development effort is in line with the Government Regulation on the general principle of state administration which includes the principle of legal certainty, the principle of orderly administration of public interests, the principle of openness, the principle of proportionality, the principle of professionalism and the principle of accountability.

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The form and mirror of accountability in the administration of regional government is by issuing several regulations, such as Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, and several Government Regulations as the implementation of the Act referred to, including Government Regulation Number 105 of 2000 and Government Regulation Number 108 of 2000 The aforementioned laws, include Government Regulation Number 105 of 2000 and Government Regulation Number 108 of 2000. In Law Number 32 of 2004, to provide governance, the Governor as the organizer of regional executive in the area of regional autonomy is responsible to the House of Representatives Regions and in their position as representatives of the Central

Government in the regions are responsible to the President. While in the administration of the government in the Regency / City, the Regent or Mayor is responsible to the Regency / City Regional People's Representative Council as a manifestation of people's sovereignty and is obliged to report to the President through the Minister of the Interior in the context of fostering and supervising.

Associated with the issue of accountability in terms of accountability, in Law Number 32 of 2004 it is expressly stated in the following articles: Article 27 paragraph (2) In addition to having the obligations referred to in paragraph (1) the regional head has the obligation to also provide an implementation report regional governments to the Government, and provide accountability statement reports to the Regional House of Representatives, as well as inform the local government implementation reports to the public; Paragraph (3) The report on the administration of the government to the Government as referred to in paragraph (2) shall be submitted to the President through the Minister of the Interior for the Governor, and the Minister of the Interior through the Governor for the Regent / Mayor 1 (one) time in 1 (one) year; Paragraph (4) The report referred to in paragraph (3) is used by the government as a basis for evaluating the administration of the regional government and as material for further guidance in accordance with statutory regulations.

As a further elaboration, a series of Government Regulations have been issued and relating to accountability, mainly reflected in Government Regulation Number 108 of 2000 concerning Regional Head Accountability Procedures and Government Regulation Number 105 of 2000 concerning Management and Accountability of Regional Finances. Government Regulation No. 108/2000 regarding the Procedures for the Responsibility of Regional Heads, is an obligation of regional governments to explain the performance of government administration to the public. In the explanation of Government Regulation Number 108, it was stated that to maintain the sustainability of the administration of regional government, in principle the tenure of the Regional Head and Deputy Regional Head is 5 (five) years. The year-end accountability of the Regional Head to the Regional Representative Council is not a vehicle to bring down the Regional Head, but it is a vehicle for evaluating and improving the performance of the regional government. The responsibility of the Regional Head to the Regional House of Representatives is not merely intended as an effort to determine the weaknesses in the implementation of the regional government but also to improve the efficiency, effectiveness, productivity and accountability of the administration of the regional government as a function of supervision by the Regional House of Representatives on the running of the government.

Furthermore, several articles in Government Regulation Number 108 of 2000 relating to accountability are as follows: Strategic planning for regional planning approved by the Regional House of Representatives and Regional Heads implemented five years that describes the vision, mission, goals, strategies, programs and activities of the region . The final annual accountability of the budget is the responsibility of the Regional Head to the Regional Representative Council for the implementation of the Regional Government for one fiscal year which is the responsibility for implementing the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget.

From the description of the mechanism and substance of this responsibility is essentially the horizontal accountability of the Regional Head to the community through the Regional People's Representative Council, the mechanism and substance of the responsibility has been started when the ratification of the Strategic Plan by the Regional People's Representative Council, hereinafter this Strategic Plan is a benchmark for the accountability of the Head Area. Then in more depth the substance of the Accountability and its period, including the accountability of the end of the fiscal year; final term of office responsibility; and accountability for certain matters. Furthermore, it is substantially stated that the accountability of the end of the fiscal year is the responsibility of the implementation of the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget. Performance appraisal based on Strategy Plan benchmarks. And the accountability of the end of the term of office is the responsibility for the general tasks of government and assistance which is the performance of the Regional Head with the term of office of the Regional Head based on the benchmark of the Strategic Plan.

Associated with financial accountability (regional financial accountability) in Government Regulation Number 105 of 2000 concerning Regional Financial Accountability, explicitly in article 37 paragraph (1) the Regional Government submits a quarterly report on the implementation of the Regional Budget for the Regional Representatives; Paragraph (2) Quarterly reports as referred to in paragraph (1) shall be submitted at the latest 1 (one) month after the end of the relevant quarterly. Then in article 38, it is stated that the Regional Head compiles a financial accountability report consisting of a report on the calculation of the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget; Note on the calculation of the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget; Cash Flow Statement; and Regional Balance Sheet.

The manifestation of this responsibility is the development of a system of accountability called the Government Institution Performance Accountability System, whose implementation starts from the preparation of the Strategic Plan to performance accountability in the form of a Government Institution Performance Accountability Report which is the result of the initiative of the State Administration Agency and the State Audit and Development Agency 2000.

One form of accountability for government performance is in terms of the effectiveness of the budget used. According to Apip (2013) in his research stated that budgeting procedures that are perceived fairly will improve

the managerial performance of the responsibility center manager, both the direct influence of perceptions of budgetary procedural justice itself and through increasing perceptions of fairness of the distribution of the budget.

In the Regional Personnel Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency itself there are still many problems related to the implementation of the system of accountability and the application of good governance, such as there are still not transparent about the process of accountability for activities with finance, performance evaluation is not according to procedures, the participation of the community, especially the House of Representatives Musi Banyuasin Regency which has not been good in overseeing the role and accountability of the performance of the Musi Banyuasin Regional Civil Service Agency. In addition, in the Regional Personnel Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency itself, which so far has assumed that the success of an institution is more emphasized on its ability to absorb budgetary resources.

In accordance with the development of science and technology, today good governance is one of the topics of discussion or important issues, so this raises questions about the capacity of good governance in government agencies. This can be achieved one of them by implementing the Government Institution Performance Accountability System at the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency. Thus not only ensuring performance improvement but also creating an environment of accountability that is encouraged and monitored. Therefore, it is expected that the implementation of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System and the application of good governance will further improve the performance of the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency itself so that progress and benefits will be felt for the community and the Musi Banyuasin District Government.

Based on the problems mentioned above, namely the application of the system of accountability that has not been measured and legitimate also the application of the principle of good governance that is not yet perfect, the authors are interested in the characteristics that want to be studied for further research, which the writer formulates with the title: The Government of the Implementation of Good Governance in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency, South Sumatra Province.

II. Methodology

The research method used in this study is a descriptive analytical method with a survey approach. According to Moh. Nasir (2005: 54) argues that the analytical descriptive method is "A method in examining the status of a human group, object, a condition, a system of thought, or a class of events in the present." While the survey method according to Sugiyono (2006: 7) is as follows: "Research conducted on large and small populations, but the data studied are data from samples taken from these populations, so that relative events, distribution, and relationship are found. the relationship between sociological and psychological variables "

Population and Withdrawal Samples

In this study, the target population that the writer examined was the subject related to the implementation of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System in relation to the implementation of good governance, namely Civil Servants employees in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency as many as 54 people. The sampling technique in this study is to use the purposive sampling technique that is the technique of determining the sample with certain considerations (adjusted to the objectives and research problems), the elements chosen as samples are limited to the elements that can provide information based on certain considerations (Ety Rochaety and Ratih Tresnawati, 2007: 66). Therefore, the sample used in this study is only the Civil Servants of the Musi Banyuasin District Civil Service Agency that relates to the Government Institution Performance Accountability System and the application of good governance, amounting to 33 people.

Data analysis method

The method used to process and analyze data in this study is an associative analysis that uses correlation coefficient analysis to determine the level of closeness of the relationship between the variables studied, then the coefficient of determination analysis is also used to determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Correlation coefficient analysis used is the moment product correlation coefficient is formulated as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum x_1 y_1 - (\sum x_1)(\sum y_1)}{\sqrt{\{n \sum x_1^2 - (\sum x_1)^2\} \{n \sum y_1^2 - (\sum y_1)^2\}}} \dots\dots\dots(\text{Arikunto : 2002:157})$$

To be able to provide an interpretation of the coefficients obtained from the results of these calculations, it can be seen in the following conditions:

Table 1: Guidelines for Providing Interpretation of Correlation Coefficients

Relationship	Coefficient Interval
0.00-0.199	Very Low
0.20-0.399	Low
0,40-0,599	Medium
0.60-0.799	Strong
0,80-1,000	Very strong

Source: (Sugiyono 2004:1830)

Analysis of the coefficient of determination is the square of the correlation value (r^2). This analysis is used to determine the magnitude of the influence of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System for the implementation of good governance which is formulated as follows:

$$Kd = r^2 \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots(\text{Sujana 2002:246})$$

Hypothesis testing will begin with the determination of operational hypotheses, determination of the level of significance, test of significance, criteria and drawing conclusions.

H0: $\rho_{Yx} = 0$, There is no significant influence on the Accountability System variable Government Instant Performance Accountability System Performance of Government Agencies towards Good Governance

HA: $\rho_{Yx} \neq 0$, There is a significant influence on the Accountability System variable Performance of Government Agencies Accountability System Performance of Government Agencies towards Good Governance

To test the significance of the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable t test was used. t value can be determined by the following formula:

$$t_{hitung} = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

Variable Measurement Instrument

In the research there are two, namely the Implementation of Government Institution Performance Accounting System (PAS) as an independent variable and the Implementation of Good Governance as the dependent. Implementation of Government Agency Performance Accountability System (PAS). The instrument used to measure the Variables of Government Institution Performance Accounting System (PAS) and the Implementation of Good Governance is a questionnaire.

Government Institution Performance Accountability System is basically an instrument used by government agencies in fulfilling the obligations to account for the success and failure of the implementation of the organization's mission. To find out the Implementation of Government Institution Performance Accountability System is measured using a questionnaire with a 5 point Likert scale. The points raised were about the level of implementation of the 5 elements of the Government Agency Performance Accountability System, which consists of: (1). Strategic Plan, (2) Work Plan, (3) Performance Measurement, (4) Performance Evaluation, (5) Performance Accountability Analysis.

Good Governance is the implementation of solid and responsible development management that is in line with the democratization of markets and efficient markets, avoidance of misallocation and scarce

investment funds and prevention of corruption both politically and administratively, as well as carrying out budgetary discipline and creating a legal and political framework for growing activities entrepreneur. In the questionnaire it was asked about the extent to which the principles of good governance developed by UNDP have been realized, which consist of (1) Participation, (2) Law Ability, (3) Transparency, (4) Responsive, (5) Equality, (6) Effectiveness and Efficiency, (7) Accountability, (8) Strategic Vision.

III. Results of Implementation of Government Institution Performance Accountability System at the Regional Personnel Agency Musi Banyuasin

Based on the answers of respondents to the questions that researchers presented through a questionnaire to get an overview of the implementation of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin District, the results show that the implementation of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency is relatively good. This is evidenced by the answers of respondents, where most respondents gave positive answers on a score of 4 (positive) and 5 (very positive), although there were still respondents who answered on a score of 3 (quite positive). The following are the results of the respondents' answers regarding the implementation of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System at the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency. The following is a table of the results of the respondents' answers to the variable questions Implementation of Government Agency Performance Accountability System (X):

Table 2: Respondents' Results for Variable Questions X

Item Question	Score	Average score
1	145	149,85
2	149	
3	153	
4	147	
5	149	
6	148	
7	148	
8	147	
9	149	
10	152	
11	154	
12	151	
13	156	
Total	1.948	

The following is an interval classification table to provide an overview of the assessment of the implementation of the Government Agency Performance Accountability System at the Regional Civil Service Agency office in Musi Banyuasin Regency:

Table 3: Classification of Intervals in Implementing Government Accountability Performance System

Rating Interval	Classification
429-770,2	Not good
771,2-1114,4	Not good

1115,4-1458,6	Pretty good
1459,6-1802,8	Good
1803,8-2145	Very good

From the results of data processing obtained from table 5 above, the total score obtained is 1,948, so if it is connected with the interval classification it is located between 1803.8-2145 with a very good answer category. So in general it can be concluded that the implementation of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System (PAS) in Musi Banyuasin Regency BKD has been implemented relatively well, but it has not been carried out optimally. This means that the implementation of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System at the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency can still be improved.

Implementation of Good Governance in Regional Personnel Agencies Musi Banyuasin Regency

Based on the answers from respondents to the questions presented by researchers through a questionnaire to get an overview of the application of Good Governance in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin, the results show that the application of Good Governance in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency is relatively good. This is evidenced by the answers of respondents, where most respondents gave positive answers on a score of 4 (positive) and 5 (very positive), although there were still respondents who answered on a score of 3 (quite positive).

The following is a table of the results of the respondents' answers to the variable Y questions (Applying Good Governance):

Table 4: Results of Respondents' Answers to Variable Questions Y

Item Questions	Score	Average score
1	145	151,15
2	152	
3	150	
4	146	
5	152	
6	153	
7	153	
8	155	
9	158	
10	151	
11	149	
12	148	
13	153	
Total	1965	

The following is an interval classification table to provide an overview of the assessment of the implementation of Good Governance in the Regional Civil Service Office of Musi Banyuasin Regency:

Table 5: Classification Intervals for Implementing Good Governance

Rating Interval	Classification
429-770,2	Not good
771,2-1114,4	Not good
1115,4-1458,6	Pretty good
1459,6-1802,8	Good
1803,8-2145	Very good

From the results of data processing obtained from table 7 above, the total score obtained is 1965, so when it is connected with the interval classification it is located between 1803.8-2145 with a very good answer category. So in general it can be concluded that the implementation of good governance in Musi Banyuasin Regency has been implemented relatively well, but it has not been done optimally. This means that the application of good governance in the Musi Banyuasin can still be increased again

Hypothesis Testing Results

This analysis is used to find relationships and test the hypotheses of the influence of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System and Good Governance. This analysis begins with the calculation of the correlation coefficient as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum x_1 y_1 - (\sum x_1)(\sum y_1)}{\sqrt{\{n \sum x_1^2 - (\sum x_1)^2\} \{n \sum y_1^2 - (\sum y_1)^2\}}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{33 \sum 117.250 - (\sum 1.952)(\sum 1.975)}{\sqrt{\{33 \sum 115.918 - (\sum 3.810.304)\} \{33 \sum 119.215 - (\sum 3.900.625)\}}}$$

$$r_{xy} = 0,627$$

Based on the calculation of the Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPM) above which produces a value of $r = 0.627$ and refers to Table 4 Interpretation of Correlation Coefficient of Value r , it can be concluded that the correlation between Government Accountability System Performance (X) variables with Good Governance (Y) variables is indicated strongly .

Analysis of the coefficient of determination is the square of the correlation value (r^2). This analysis is used to determine the magnitude of the influence of Government Institution Performance Accountability Systems on the implementation of Good Governance. Here are the formulas and calculations of the coefficient of determination analysis:

$$Kd = r^2 \times 100\%$$

$$Kd = 0,627^2 \times 100\% = 39,3\%$$

To test the significance of the influence of the independent variable Accountability System Performance of Government Agencies (X) on the dependent variable Good Governance (Y) used the t test. The value of t can be determined by the following formula:

$$t \text{ count} =$$

$$\frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

$$t \text{ count} =$$

$$\frac{0,627\sqrt{33-2}}{\sqrt{1-0,627^2}}$$

$$= 4,481$$

With $dk = 32$ ($n-1 = 33-1$) and a significance level (α) of 5% obtained t table 3,622; thus $t_{count} > t_{table}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Then it can be concluded that there is a significant influence on Government Institution Performance Accountability System variables on Good Governance.

IV. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Implementation of Government Institution Performance Accountability System
2. Regional Personnel Agency Musi Banyuasin Regency, including very good classification. The assessment is measured using Strategic Planning indicators, Performance Plans, Performance Measurement, Performance Evaluation and Performance Accountability Analysis.

3. The Implementation of Good Governance in the Regional Civil Service Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency is included in the very good classification. The assessment is measured using indicators of participation, law abiding, transparency, responsiveness, equality, effectiveness and efficiency, accountability, and strategic vision.
4. The implementation of the Government Institution Performance Accountability System has a significant effect on the implementation of Good Governance in the Regional Personnel Agency office in Musi Banyuasin. This means that if the implementation of the Government Agency Performance Accountability System is getting better, then the implementation of Good Governance in the Regional Personnel Agency of Musi Banyuasin Regency will be even better.

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